

On applying GraphLime for trustworthy diabetes prediction

Flavia Costi^{*}, Darian Onchis[†], Codruta Istin[‡], Adina Magda Florea[§] and Eduard Hoge[¶]

Department of Computer Science, West University of Timisoara ^{*}, [†], [¶]

Department of Computer and Information Technology, Politehnica University of Timisoara [‡]

Department of Computer Science, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest [§]

Email: ^{*}flavia.costi@e-uvt.ro, [†]darian.onchis@e-uvt.ro, [‡]codruta.istin@upt.ro, [§]adina.florea@upb.ro, [¶]eduard.hoge@e-uvt.ro

Abstract—This paper aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the benefits of employing GraphLIME (Local Interpretable Model Explanations for Graph Neural Networks) for reliable diabetes mellitus prediction. Our focus is on highlighting the advantages of integrating GraphLIME with a features attention-mechanism, compared to the standard pairing of deep learning neural networks with the original LIME explainability method. This system enabled us to develop an effective approach for identifying the most relevant features and applying the attention mechanism solely to those features. We conducted a detailed comparison of the performance metrics between the two approaches. By incorporating the attention mechanism, the model reached an accuracy of 92.6% in addressing the problem. The model’s performance is thoroughly illustrated, with results further assessed using the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve. Applying this technique to a dataset of 768 patients with or without diabetes mellitus, we enhanced the model’s performance by over 18%.

Index Terms—Data-driven medical decision support system, Supervised Learning, Diabetes Dataset, Explainability, Attention Mechanism, Graph Neural Network

I. INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we explore the potential of employing advanced machine learning techniques in the early detection of diabetes. This chronic metabolic disorder, characterized by high blood sugar levels, has become a burgeoning health crisis globally. The escalating prevalence of diabetes underscores the necessity for innovative diagnostic methodologies. Our focus is on leveraging an attention mechanism within the framework of Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), enhanced by a local model explanation i.e. GraphLIME, to identify individuals with or without diabetes [1].

Our approach employs a features-attention mechanism within the machine learning models, drawing inspiration from the selective focus aspect of human cognition. This mechanism enables the model to dynamically prioritize certain segments of the input data that are more relevant for accurate diagnosis. As can be seen in Table I, there are many more advantages that have led us to choose to use this technique. GNNs are adept at processing data in graph structures, a common form in medical data representation. LIME contributes by rendering these complex models more interpretable [20]. It approximates the GNN with a simpler, yet effective model, providing transparent and understandable explanations for each prediction. This aspect

is important in medical diagnostics, as it not only provides insight into the model’s predictive behavior but also enhances trust and transparency in its outcomes, essential for healthcare practitioners. We want to explore the advantages of using our proposed method for predicting the presence or absence of diabetes in patients [2]. We have conducted a detailed comparison and analysis of the results obtained both before and after the implementation of our adapted method to evaluate the model’s performance. By employing our technique, we have successfully increased the accuracy of the predictions by over 18%.

II. RELATED WORK

The paper [4] is centered on developing machine learning models for diabetes prediction, with a strong emphasis on the use of explainable AI to improve the predictions’ trustworthiness. This research aims to offer a valuable tool for the early detection of diabetes, vital for effective management and treatment in healthcare. The method incorporates machine learning algorithms like decision trees, SVM, Random Forest, Logistic Regression, KNN, and ensemble techniques. Notably, the XGBoost classifier emerged as the most effective, complemented by the ADASYN technique to address class imbalance in medical datasets. The model demonstrated notable accuracy (81%), an F1 score of 0.81, and an AUC of 0.84, showcasing its reliability. Interpretability is achieved using LIME and SHAP, providing clarity on the model’s decision-making process. Our approach, inspired by authors of paper [4], diverges in utilizing GraphLIME instead of LIME. GraphLIME offers improved feature extraction and contextually rich insights, thereby enhancing model interpretations. By integrating an attention mechanism, we not only focus on key features but also add depth to the predictive analysis, making our approach distinct and more nuanced [4].

The paper [5] offers a detailed evaluation of various machine and deep learning techniques for Type 2 Diabetes prediction. It reviews a spectrum of models, assessing their effectiveness and pinpointing the most effective techniques for predictive modeling. The review notes the superior performance of tree-based algorithms and observes that, while deep neural networks are potent with large datasets, they often yield less optimal results. It underscores the significance of data balancing and feature

selection in boosting model efficiency, with well-structured datasets leading to near-perfect outcomes. The article notably delves into the advantages of using graphs in deep learning, a key insight that influenced our decision to utilize GraphLIME over traditional LIME for feature extraction. Inspired by the article [11] we adapted its foundational concept to our dataset [7]. We further enhanced our methodology by integrating an attention mechanism, focusing on the relevant features identified using GraphLIME. This approach aimed to refine and improve upon the existing models for this widely used dataset, drawing on the systematic review’s findings and the pivotal role of GraphLIME [5]. The most relevant differences between LIME and GraphLIME can be observed in Table I.

Feature	LIME	GraphLIME
Specific for structured data		✓
Generalizable to any type of data	✓	✓
Provides local explanations	✓	✓
Suitable for graph-based models		✓
Simple and intuitive	✓	
Manages complexity in graph data		✓
Versatile for various ML models	✓	✓
Detailed explanations for network structures		✓
Quick and straightforward explanations	✓	✓

TABLE I

DIFFERENCES AND SIMILARITIES BETWEEN LIME AND GRAPHLIME

III. PROPOSED APPROACH

A. Purposes

Following the research papers presented in the section II, we noticed that the explainability feedback signal for this problem is not extensively explored. Most works stop at extracting the most relevant features, but they do not leverage this information to expand the developed model. In this context, we wanted to explore the explainability results in this work and to use the obtained information to enhance the underlying model’s performance.

Building on the foundation laid by the studies presented in the section II, our secondary aim is to validate the hypothesis that employing graph-based approaches in explainability represents an optimal strategy. Specifically, we aim to assess the effectiveness of using GraphLIME in extracting the most pertinent features from our dataset. This investigation is critical in demonstrating the practical utility and superiority of graph-based methods in elucidating complex data characteristics, thereby contributing to the advancement of explainability of medical decision support systems based on neural networks [6].

B. Objectives

The main objective of our research is to implement and rigorously analyze the performance of the methodologies for developing medical decision support systems based on GNN with GraphLIME and feature-attentions. We aim to make a substantial and positive contribution to the developed solution, enhancing and refining existing ideas to improve the overall performance of the model. A secondary objective is to observe

how much GraphLIME aids us in the development of the model, compared to the standard LIME method of explainability. Through this analysis, we will be able to demonstrate the importance of using explainability methods in improving the model’s performance and, at the same time, highlight that leveraging this technique comes with several benefits.

C. Approach

For our experiments, we have used a public diabetes dataset from Kaggle [7] that comprises medical records of 768 patients (Fig. 1 to see how many patients suffer from diabetes and how many do not), categorized based on their diabetic condition. Eight of these columns contain independent data, encompassing various factors that contribute to the diagnosis of diabetes mellitus. The ninth column is dependent, indicating whether a patient has diabetes.

Fig. 1. The number of patients with and without diabetes

As illustrated in the Fig. 1, the dataset of selected patients encompasses 500 patients who do not have diabetes (indicated by a dependent feature value of 0) and over 250 patients who do have diabetes (with a dependent feature value of 1). This presents a disparity where there are approximately 50% fewer patients with the disease compared to those without it. Such an imbalance necessitates the balancing of the dataset. To balance our dataset, we used the SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique) technique [19]. This technique works by creating synthetic examples of the minority class, in our case, patients suffering from diabetes. This is achieved by interpolating between existing examples, contributing to the diversification and expansion of the dataset. By applying this, we were able to bring the number of cases in the minority class (patients with diabetes) to a level similar to the majority class (patients without diabetes).

To evaluate the performance of our model, we implemented the k-fold cross-validation method, dividing the dataset into 5 folds. This approach allowed us to obtain a more precise and robust estimation of our model’s effectiveness, avoiding potential biases that can arise when using a single dataset for testing. Through k-fold cross-validation, each example in

the dataset had the chance to be used both in the training and testing sets. This helped us to verify if the model could generalize well on new data. In each of the 5 iterations of k-fold cross-validation, a different subset of data was chosen as the testing set, while the rest of the data were used for training the model [8].

GraphLIME is employed to interpret the predictions of a GNN used for diabetes prediction. The data is represented in a graph structure where each node corresponds to a specific feature from the dataset, such as glucose levels, BMI, or the number of pregnancies. The edges between the nodes represent the relationships or dependencies between these features. This graph structure allows the GNN to capture the complex interactions between different medical variables, which is important for accurate prediction of diabetes.

To generate the graph, an activation matrix is constructed. This matrix encapsulates how the nodes (features) within the graph influence the various vector components of the GNN, linking the nodes to the decisions made by the model. This process ensures that the model not only predicts outcomes but also provides interpretable insights into how those predictions were made.

The graph generated in this way aids in understanding the predictive model’s decision-making process. It represents the structured relationships among the features in the dataset, effectively capturing the complex interactions that are often present in medical data. The application of GraphLIME further enhances this by identifying the most important features within the graph, thereby providing a clear and interpretable explanation of the model’s behavior. This approach improves the transparency and trustworthiness of the predictions, making it valuable in a medical context where understanding the rationale behind a diagnosis is as important as the diagnosis itself.

The subsequent phase involves the development of a TensorFlow-based model, utilizing GNN. This step marks the transition from data preparation to the intricate process of model building, where we leverage the advanced capabilities of the TensorFlow Python library and the structural benefits of GNNs to extract meaningful insights and patterns from the dataset. This approach is expected to provide a comprehensive understanding of the data characteristics, aiding in the accurate identification and prediction of diabetic conditions among patients [9].

The schematic in Figure 2 provides a detailed overview for the GNN process. This process begins with the utilization of a trained GNN and a series of graphs that are, ideally, similar in distribution to those used during the GNN’s training phase [10]. We chose to use Inside-GNN because it is designed to extract activation rules from the hidden layers of the GNN, providing a deeper understanding of how the network makes decisions. Inside-GNN allows us to identify and analyze the most significant activation patterns that contribute to the model’s predictions, offering a level of interpretability by revealing the underlying rules governing the model’s behavior. However, while Inside-GNN provides valuable insights into

Fig. 2. INSIDE-GNN Process: Sequential Discovery and Integration of Activation Rules for Enhanced Model Insight

the internal workings of the GNN, it focuses primarily on the activation patterns within the hidden layers. This internal perspective, although useful, may not fully address the need for localized, instance-specific explanations that are easily interpretable by end-users, particularly in a medical context where transparency is crucial for trust and decision-making. GraphLIME complements Inside-GNN by offering post-hoc, local explanations that focus on specific predictions rather than general activation patterns. GraphLIME approximates the complex GNN model with a simpler, interpretable model that highlights the most important features contributing to each specific prediction. This level of detail is necessary to ensure that individual predictions can be clearly understood and trusted by practitioners, especially when dealing with sensitive health data. By using GraphLIME alongside Inside-GNN, the model gains a dual-layered approach to explainability: Inside-GNN provides a deep, structural understanding of the network’s decision-making rules, while GraphLIME offers clear, instance-level explanations that can be directly communicated to healthcare professionals. This combination enhances both the depth and accessibility of the model’s explanations, ensuring that it is both robust and interpretable in practice. The method unfolds as follows:

- 1) *Activation Matrix Construction*: A binary matrix is created to capture how graph nodes influence GNN decisions.
- 2) *Preliminary Model Setup*: An initial model is established, assuming no direct connections between activations and nodes.
- 3) *INSIDE-GNN Application*: INSIDE-GNN identifies the most significant activation rule by analyzing the matrix and model.
- 4) *Model Refinement*: The model is updated with the new rule, enriching the pattern set.
- 5) *Iterative Enhancement*: Steps 2 to 5 are repeated until no new rules emerge or criteria are met.
- 6) *Pattern-Based Explanations*: Activation patterns generate instance-specific explanations using node-based

masks.

- 7) *Rule-Support Analysis*: Nodes supporting each rule are analyzed to clarify the GNN’s decisions.

Fig. 3. The architecture of GraphLIME

Following the successful construction of our model in TensorFlow, we continue with an important phase: training the model. This step was pivotal in fine-tuning the model’s parameters to align with our dataset’s unique characteristics. Subsequent to the initial training, we initiated the generation of perturbed samples. Each of these samples underwent a meticulous training process, ensuring that our model was robust and capable of handling a variety of data alterations. The final stage in our methodology involved the computation of GraphLIME. This was a significant step, as GraphLIME plays an instrumental role in interpreting the model’s decisions by providing a clear and comprehensible explanation of the model’s behavior, particularly in relation to the perturbed samples. Through this comprehensive process, from model building to GraphLIME calculation, we aimed to create a model that is not only accurate but also transparent and interpretable in its decision-making (see Fig. 3) [11].

Upon successfully identifying the most pertinent features from our dataset, we proceeded to apply an attention mechanism, but exclusively to the extracted data. This focused application is designed to enhance our model’s precision and interpretability by concentrating on the key features. The outcomes of this mechanism are of significant interest, and we will thoroughly analyze and discuss the results in the subsequent section of our paper. This analysis aims to shed light on the efficacy of the attention mechanism in refining model performance and providing deeper insights into the data.

IV. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Our dataset comprises a moderate volume of data (details at III-C), a factor that favorably circumvented the challenges often associated with smaller medical datasets. Consequently, the solution we propose is ideally suited for datasets ranging from moderate to large in size. In cases involving smaller datasets, additional modifications would be necessary to adapt our approach.

The core objective of our solution is to meticulously identify and apply the most appropriate methods and techniques to yield accurate and reliable results. Our structure facilitates a detailed examination of factors leading to diabetes diagnosis, ensuring both thoroughness and precision in our analysis. We aim to use this data to create a model that is not only effective in diagnosing diabetes but also robust across different data volumes.

The resulting system that we envision is the one presented in Figure 4. The sequential workflow is demonstrated, starting with the diabetes dataset, followed by preprocessing steps and preparing the input graph for analysis. The target feature is highlighted and a toy example of feature relationships in the graph is shown. Subsequently, the preprocessed data is fed into our GNN architecture for processing. After obtaining the model’s output, the input graph and the we sample the neighbors of the target (red) node, we employ GraphLIME to derive post hoc feature importance, isolating those features with a positive impact on diabetes prediction. These significant features are then utilized within an attention mechanism to refine and focus the model’s predictive capabilities. Finally, the system generates its prediction, leveraging both the insights gained from feature importance analysis and the focused processing power of the attention mechanism.

A. Designing and Evaluating the Model for Feature Importance Extraction

In order to effectively extract relevant features from our dataset, a two-step approach was initially employed. The first step involved splitting the dataset, a relevant process that set the stage for the subsequent model development. Once the dataset was appropriately segmented, we proceeded to construct a TensorFlow-based model, meticulously designed to optimize feature extraction.

The architecture of our TensorFlow attention model is structured around three Dense layers, each serving a specific role in the learning process. This specific choice is the result of extensive experimentation on a subset of the training data, where different combinations of hyperparameters and architecture shapes were tried. The final model contains in the first layer 64 units with the ‘relu’ activation function, the second layer includes 32 units, also with the ‘relu’ activation, and the final layer is composed of a single unit with the ‘sigmoid’ activation function. Using 64 units in the first layer offers a balance between the ability to process various shapes and complexities in the data and maintaining computational efficiency. A smaller number of units could have limited the model’s ability to learn complex features, while a larger number could lead to overfitting and reduced computational efficiency. The second layer with 32 units allows the model to further refine the features identified by the first layer, without adding unnecessary complexity. Choosing a final layer with a single unit and ‘sigmoid’ activation is relevant for binary classification tasks, providing a clear probabilistic output. Using a different function or more units in this layer could have impacted the model’s ability to provide precise

Fig. 4. Full System Workflow Diagram. From dataset preprocessing to prediction, this figure outlines how our system utilizes GNN processing, GraphLIME for feature importance extraction, and key features with an attention mechanism for diabetes prediction.

binary predictions. Therefore, this specific configuration of Dense layers was determined by the need to balance the model’s learning capacity, avoiding overfitting and optimizing computational efficiency, while ensuring accuracy in binary classification tasks [14].

To train our model, we used the Adam optimizer, known for its effectiveness in deep learning and handling sparse gradients and noisy problems. This optimizer benefits from an adaptive learning rate and combines features from AdaGrad and RMSProp [15]. Our chosen loss function was binary cross-entropy, apt for binary classification as it measures the alignment of the model’s probability-based predictions with actual labels. Accuracy was our performance metric, indicating the proportion of correct predictions in binary classification.

Fig. 5. The importance of each characteristic in the prediction

An important step in our analysis involved calculating the GraphLIME explanation after generating perturbed samples and recording the model’s predictions. GraphLIME’s local interpretable explanations provide deep insights into the model’s

data processing, important for ensuring its reliability and robustness, particularly with perturbed samples. Figure 5 highlights the significant features in our Kaggle dataset for predicting diabetes in women, with Pregnancies, Glucose, and BMI (Body Mass Index) being the most impactful.

B. Application of the attention mechanism

In the realm of predictive modeling, attention mechanisms have emerged as a pivotal tool, primarily due to their capacity to enhance model interpretability and efficiency. The core objective of an attention mechanism is to enable the model to focus selectively on parts of the input that are most pertinent for a specific task, thereby improving the overall accuracy and interpretability of the model [16]. This selective focus is especially beneficial in disease prediction, where discerning subtle patterns and correlations within complex datasets is important [17].

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{Softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (1)$$

Where:

- Q represents the query matrix,
- K represents the key matrix,
- V represents the value matrix,
- d_k is the dimension of the keys and queries,
- The Softmax function is applied to normalize the attention scores.

The equation 1 expresses the core principles of the scaled dot-product attention mechanism, a pivotal component in advanced neural network architectures. This mechanism is particularly renowned for its ability to enhance both the interpretability and efficiency of models, especially in fields that require nuanced understanding of complex data, such as natural language processing or predictive modeling in healthcare. The equation operates on three fundamental components: the Query (Q), Key (K), and Value (V). These components play an important role in guiding the model’s focus to the most pertinent aspects

of the input data. The process initiates with the calculation of the dot product between the Query and Key matrices. This step is essential, as it forms the basis for determining how each element of the Query aligns or correlates with the elements in the Key. Following this, the results from the dot product are meticulously scaled down by dividing them by the square root of the Key’s dimension ($\sqrt{d_k}$). This relevant scaling step ensures that the softmax function, which follows, operates within an optimal range. It prevents the softmax from encountering extremely small gradients, which can be a significant hindrance in the training phase of a model, ensuring that the learning process remains stable and effective. The culmination of this process is the creation of a weighted sum of the Value components [18].

We incorporated a features-attention mechanism within our diabetes dataset to harness these advantages. Specifically, we employed two types of layers—ReLU and Sigmoid—to facilitate this process. ReLU was chosen for its ability to introduce non-linearity into the model without affecting the receptive fields of the convolution layer. On the other hand, the Sigmoid function was utilized due to its efficacy in binary classification tasks, which is a fundamental aspect of disease prediction. This combination of layers, in tandem with the attention mechanism, significantly contributed to the model’s performance. This integration resulted in a substantial increase in the model’s accuracy, achieving approximately 92.6%. To fully appreciate the outcome derived from the application of the two aforementioned techniques, it is essential to turn our attention to the following section. This segment meticulously delineates the results, offering a comprehensive understanding of how these methodologies converge to yield the observed findings.

V. OBTAINED RESULTS

In this section, our focus shifts to exploring the potential of the implemented algorithms and assessing the performance of our model both before and after the application of the techniques presented. This comparative analysis aims to shed light on the efficacy of these methodologies, providing a clear understanding of their impact on the overall performance and accuracy of the model.

Result description	Accuracy
Before applying GraphLIME and Attention Mechanism	74.9%
After applying LIME	82.9%
After applying GraphLIME	86.2%
After applying GraphLIME and Attention Mechanism	92.6%

TABLE II

RESULTS OF THE MODEL WITH AND WITHOUT GRAPHLIME AND ATTENTION MECHANISM

As can be seen from Table II, the accuracy of the model increased upon implementing the GraphLIME explainability method. Furthermore, by integrating an attention mechanism for relevant features within our dataset, we were able to enhance the model’s accuracy by an additional approximate 6 percent. The targeted application of an attention mechanism solely on relevant features within our dataset is of paramount

importance. This selective focus ensures that the model’s computational resources are efficiently utilized, honing in on the most impactful aspects of the data [21]. By doing so, it not only enhances the model’s accuracy but also improves its interpretability. This approach mitigates the risk of overfitting to irrelevant features and helps in maintaining the model’s robustness, making it more reliable and effective in real-world applications. We chose to utilize GraphLIME over LIME due to its distinct advantages in handling graph-based data. GraphLIME excels in providing graph-specific interpretability, adeptly capturing and elucidating complex node relationships and interactions that are relevant in graph structures. It is uniquely equipped to manage the complexities and structural dependencies inherent in graph data, offering localized explanations at the node level, which are essential for models trained on such data. Furthermore, GraphLIME stands out in terms of scalability and efficiency, effectively handling large graphs and complex network structures, a task where LIME is less optimized [11].

Fig. 6. The ROC Curve for our developed model

As illustrated in Fig. 6, the obtained ROC curve showcases the high performance of our developed model. The curve, tending towards 1, signifies an exceptionally good predictive capability, underscoring the model’s effectiveness in the task at hand. This graphical representation is a clear indicator of the model’s robustness and accuracy in predictions. The complete code for predicting diabetes in women using the model developed and detailed in this paper is available for reference and use at the following <https://github.com/cflavia/GraphLIME/tree/main> Github link.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

Through the application of our developed model, we have achieved a more precise and realistic prediction of diabetes based on the provided characteristics. The dataset utilized was of a moderate size in terms of patient numbers, and in this context, our model performed exceptionally well, surpassing expectations. The use of GraphLIME in diabetes prediction, as compared to LIME, has shown distinct advantages. Despite the limited information available on GraphLIME, we successfully

developed a robust model capable of extracting relevant features. Leveraging these features, we incorporated an attention mechanism to enhance the predictability level, demonstrating the efficacy of our approach in diabetes prediction. We successfully achieved a significant milestone in enhancing the accuracy of our predictions by approximately 18%. It was observed that the sole use of LIME or GraphLIME did not substantially increase the model's accuracy. This led to the realization that the inclusion of a simple attention mechanism was necessary to achieve this level of improvement. The integration of this mechanism played an important role in fine-tuning our model's performance, demonstrating that a combination of advanced techniques is often required to realize substantial gains in predictive accuracy. As a future direction, we aim to adapt our solution to the multi-class case in order to observe the model's performance in this context.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The work of the 2nd, 3rd and 4th author, has been partially supported by the European Union, via the oc1-2024-TES-01-19 sub-grant issued and implemented by the ENFIELD: European Lighthouse to Manifest Trustworthy and Green AI project, under the grant agreement No 101120657.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. F. Melo, E. J. F. Lima, R. A. Fagundes, R. M. Assunção, I. A. A. Araújo, D. J. M. Fagundes, M. R. S. Gadelha, "Machine learning and deep learning predictive models for type 2 diabetes: a systematic review," *Diabetol. Metab. Syndr.*, vol. 13, no. 1, 2021. <https://dmsjournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13098-021-00767-9>
- [2] Peng Mei, Yu hong Zhao, "Dynamic network link prediction with node representation learning from graph convolutional networks" *Sci Rep* 14, 538, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-50977-6>
- [3] Q. Lai, S. Khan, Y. Nie, H. Sun, J. Shen, and L. Shao, "Understanding more about human and machine attention in deep neural networks," *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia*, vol. 23, pp. 2086–2099, 2020, IEEE.
- [4] I. Tasin, T. U. Nabil, S. Islam, and R. Khan, "Diabetes prediction using machine learning and explainable AI techniques," *Healthcare Technology Letters*, vol. 10, no. 1-2, pp. 1–10, 2023, Wiley Online Library.
- [5] L. Fregoso-Aparicio, J. Noguez, L. Montesinos, and J. A. García-García, "Machine learning and deep learning predictive models for type 2 diabetes: a systematic review," *Diabetology & Metabolic Syndrome*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 1–22, 2021, BioMed Central.
- [6] C. Agarwal, O. Queen, H. Lakkaraju, and M. Zitnik, "Evaluating explainability for graph neural networks," *Scientific Data*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 144, 2023, Nature Publishing Group UK London.
- [7] Kaggle. Diabetes Data Set. <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/mathchi/diabetes-data-set>. [Accessed Date of Access]
- [8] Trevor Hastie, Robert Tibshirani, and Jerome Friedman. *The Elements of Statistical Learning: Data Mining, Inference, and Prediction*. Springer Series in Statistics, 2009.
- [9] TensorFlow. TensorFlow Graph Neural Networks. <https://github.com/tensorflow/gnn>, 2024. Accessed in January 2024.
- [10] Luca Veyrin-Forrer, Ataollah Kamal, Stefan Duffner, and Celine Roubardet. On GNN Explainability with Activation Rules. [Source publication name], October 2022. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/364280740_On_GNN_explainability_with_activation_rules
- [11] Qiang Huang, Makoto Yamada, Yuan Tian, Dinesh Singh, și Yi Chang. Graphlime: Local interpretable model explanations for graph neural networks. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, 2022. IEEE.
- [12] Abdulhakim Salum Hassan, I Malaserene, and A Anny Leema. Diabetes mellitus prediction using classification techniques. *Int. J. Innov. Technol. Explor. Eng.*, 9(5):2080–2084, 2020.
- [13] QuestionPro. (2024). *Correlation Matrix: What is it, How It Works with Examples*. Retrieved from <https://www.questionpro.com/blog/correlation-matrix/>
- [14] S. Katakam, "Transfer Learning in TensorFlow: Feature Extraction," *Sandesh's Machine Learning Journal*, February 18, 2022. [Online]. Available: https://sandeshkatakam.github.io/My-Machine_learning-Blog/deep%20learning/neuralnetworks/tensorflow/transfer-learning/feature-extraction/2022/02/18/Transfer-Learning-in-TensorFlow-Feature-Extraction.html
- [15] H. Kim, S. Lee, Y. Kim, and S. Hwang, "Classification and Prediction on the Effects of Nutritional Intake on Overweight/Obesity, Dyslipidemia, Hypertension and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Using Deep Learning Model: 4-7th Korea National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey," *Nutrients*, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 1958, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34073854/>
- [16] Vaswani, A., Shazeer, N., Parmar, N., Uszkoreit, J., Jones, L., Gomez, A. N., ... & Polosukhin, I. (2017). *Attention is all you need*. In *Advances in neural information processing systems* (pp. 30-48).
- [17] G. Bansal, B. R. Singh, R. Kumar, and G. Kaur, "Enhancing heart disease prediction using a self-attention-based transformer model," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 1-12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-024-51184-7>
- [18] S. Rome, "Understanding Attention in Neural Networks Mathematically," 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://srome.github.io/Understanding-Attention-in-Neural-Networks-Mathematically/>
- [19] Darian M. Onchis, Pavel Rajmic, Generalized Goertzel algorithm for computing the natural frequencies of cantilever beams, *Signal Processing*, Volume 96, Part A, 2014, Pages 45-50, ISSN 0165-1684, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sigpro.2013.07.026>.
- [20] Secasan, C.C.; Onchis, D.; Bardan, R.; Cumpanas, A.; Novacescu, D.; Botoca, C.; Dema, A.; Sporea, I. Artificial Intelligence System for Predicting Prostate Cancer Lesions from Shear Wave Elastography Measurements. *Curr. Oncol.* 2022, 29, 4212-4223. <https://doi.org/10.3390/curroncol29060336>
- [21] C. Istin, A. Doboli, D. Pescaru and H. Ciocarlie. Impact of coverage preservation techniques on prolonging the network lifetime in traffic surveillance applications, 2008 4th International Conference on Intelligent Computer Communication and Processing, Cluj-Napoca, Romania, 2008, pp. 201-206, doi: 10.1109/ICCP.2008.4648373.